

LPPD IRON BASE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The low pressure plasma deposition process can produce laminate composites where both phases are melted and deposited. FeCrAlY matrix structures reinforced with alumina and mullite have been characterized in terms of their microstructure, thermal expansion behavior, cyclic oxidation resistance, and tensile properties.

INTRODUCTION

Renewed interest is being focused on the development of high temperature materials using composites that combine the best properties of each component in the composite. The revived importance of composites is due to recognition of an immediate need for lightweight, high temperature structures possessing both high specific mechanical properties and improved damage resistance. Past work in the area of high temperature composites (useful operating life at temperatures $\geq 900^\circ\text{C}$) has consisted of incorporating the reinforcing phase in situ (i.e., directionally solidified eutectic alloys) [1,2], or incorporating the reinforcing phase, usually a filament, during fabrication [3,4]. The directionally solidified materials, although showing excellent chemical stability, are limited to systems in which a strong reinforcing eutectic phase can be produced. In addition, in eutectic systems, there are inherent limitations on the volume fraction and morphology of the second phase. These limitations are not present in the second class of composites using fiber reinforcement, but chemical stability and fabricability are severe problems. Some success has been achieved, however, in the FeCrAlY matrix-W fiber composite [3].

The problem of chemical stability of various filaments in Ti, Ni and Fe based matrices was studied extensively during the 1960's and 70's [5-7].

It has been extremely difficult to produce metal matrix composites (other than aluminum and similar low melting point matrices) using non-metallic filaments as the reinforcing phase that can survive both fabrication and long term service at temperatures $>0.5T_m$ of the matrix. For example 0.5 and $0.6T_m$ are 195 and 285°C for Al composites, 700 and 890°C for Ti composites, and 610 and 790°C for FeCrAlY composites. While Al and Ti composites will probably be used at $<0.6T_m$, the FeCrAlY composites may be used at $>0.7T_m$. The mechanism of chemical degradation for SiC and Si_3N_4 in contact with Ni-based materials has been studied in detail [8,9]. Stable coatings are available, but other difficulties, associated with fabrication, have made such systems as Al_2O_3 /Ni-base matrix unattractive to date [10]. However, the concept of coupling Al_2O_3 and a Ni-base or Fe-base matrix remains attractive, since both matrices can be modified chemically to produce stable Al_2O_3 layers when exposed to air. Compatibility between matrix and reinforcement should be easily achieved.

Developments in composite fabrication are now creating opportunities for producing a much wider range of materials combinations with designed microstructures than was previously attainable. The capability of creating lamellar microstructures can be attained through the process of low pressure plasma deposition (LPPD) [11,12]. This method is attractive both as a near-net shape fabrication process and as a technique for producing controlled microstructures to evaluate the influence of volume fraction, phase distribution, and differences in mechanical and physical behavior of the composite phases. Although the long term chemical stability between two phases still must be considered, the extremely fast fabrication time allows the incorporation of several components into a metallurgical structure with virtually no reaction. It should be recognized that the two phases in LPPD composites are not the same as in fiber composites. The reinforcement may be less effective than for filaments, but still results in a strong, stiff, low density material.

The versatility of the LPPD process to deposit a wide variety of composite microstructures is illustrated in Figure 1. A FeCrAlY matrix containing either continuous or discontinuous laminates of Al_2O_3 was produced by choosing particle sizes of each material so that both would melt in the plasma. The continuous layers were achieved by spraying each phase separately, while the discontinuous layers were made spraying powder mixtures. Similar laminate structures have been produced in metal matrices with metal, carbide and oxide reinforcements.

The process relies on a plasma formed in the gun by a high intensity electric arc discharging between a tungsten cathode and a water cooled copper anode in the presence of flowing gases. Typical gases used are Ar

Figure 1 Microstructures of FeCrAlY-alumina composites produced by LPPD: a) continuous laminate, and b) discontinuous laminate.

or N_2 with small additions of He or H_2 . Deposits are produced by injecting powders of the desired composition into the high temperature, high velocity plasma jet where they are accelerated, melted, transported, impacted and solidified on a substrate. If sprayed in air, oxidation of metal particles occurs and a porous structure (75-90 percent of theoretical density) is formed. Spraying in inert gas at atmospheric pressure, however, lessens oxidation; spraying in inert gas at low pressure (30-60 torr) nearly eliminates oxidation and results in densities generally greater than 97 percent of theoretical. Post-deposition heat treatment often is used to increase the density of plasma sprayed deposits. For LPPD superalloys, heat treatment can produce densities 100 percent of theoretical.

The rapid cooling rates involved in the LPPD process (10^5 to 10^6 °C/sec) produce an ultra-fine, as deposited grain structure (0.25-2 μ m) [13], and the avoidance of chemical segregation makes it possible to produce structures virtually impossible to duplicate by other methods. In addition, the rapid solidification and short interval between successive particle spreading promotes excellent metallurgical bonding throughout the structure. Bonding to the deposition mandrel, if desired, is enhanced by transferred arc cleaning to remove residual oxides from the substrate surface.

The study reported here is for a model composite consisting of a FeCrAlY matrix reinforced with Al_2O_3 or mullite, produced by low pressure plasma deposition. Discontinuous and continuous laminates were studied over a wide range of temperatures, measuring tensile strength, cyclic oxi-

dation behavior, and thermal expansion behavior. The microstructures produced in the oxidation testing can be used to infer the morphological stability of these composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tubular deposits were produced by spraying on pre-heated steel tubes 3.8cm in diameter and 12cm long, with the mandrel rotating and translating in the plasma. Deposits 0.1cm thick were made in times of the order of 5 minutes. Gun power levels of 70kw were used for the Ar-He plasmas, and chamber pressures were maintained at 60 torr. The FeCrAlY powder used was -325 mesh (average particle size $\sim 26\mu\text{m}$) material purchased from AMI (Troy, MI, USA) of approximate nominal composition 24 a/o Cr, 16 a/o Al, 0.3 a/o Y (AMI 970). The alumina and mullite powders, purchased from Atlantic Equipment Engineers (Bergenfield, NJ, USA) were also -325 mesh powders, with average particle size of $\sim 15\mu\text{m}$.

The deposits were heat treated 2h/1400°C in Ar and cooled in the cold zone of the furnace. Rings were cut from the tubular deposit which were 0.33cm wide, and the remnant of the steel tube mandrel was removed. The difference in contraction from the 1400°C heat treatment simplified the removal process, since the FeCrAlY matrix composites contracted less than the steel mandrel.

Thermal expansion was measured on these ring samples using a dilatometer with alumina standard, heating the pieces at a rate of 10°C/min from room temperature to 1150°C in argon. In cyclic oxidation studies, pieces of ring samples were exposed in a static air furnace at 1150°C. Samples were cooled to room temperature once each hour, for a total exposure of 1000 hours. Periodically, the samples were removed from the test so that changes in weight could be recorded. After the 1000 hour exposure, each sample was examined metallographically.

Mechanical tests were performed on the ring samples as well. Two semi-circular grips 0.03cm smaller in diameter than the inside of the ring were placed within the ring and pin loaded at a constant extension rate of 0.05cm/min [14,15]. A plot of load vs. deflection was used to determine a yield strength at an offset of 0.0025cm, the ultimate tensile strength, and the plastic deflection at failure. All mechanical tests were performed in air.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal expansion behavior is shown in Figure 2 for plasma deposited rings of FeCrAlY with nominal Al_2O_3 volume fractions of 0, 5, 15, and 25%,

together with the expansion of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The trend in the data is as expected, with behavior similar to that predicted by a rule-of-mixtures approach. In high temperature service, macroscopic stresses arising from either steady state or transient thermal gradients should be decreased for the lower expansion materials, unless this influence is offset by a higher elastic modulus in the lower expansion composites. From this consideration, the lower modulus mullite may be a preferred reinforcement for applications where thermal stress is more dominant than specific thickness.

Cyclic oxidation from room temperature to 1150°C (2100°F) showed the composite materials to be extremely resistant to the air environment. A microstructure of a composite structure is shown in Figure 3. Two samples of FeCrAlY showed weight loss during the 1000 hour exposure, but the $-2.5\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$ value is still excellent. The FeCrAlY + 5v/o Al_2O_3 lost more weight ($-5.6\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$), but the 15 and 25v/o Al_2O_3 showed only slight weight gain (1.8 and $2.0\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$), respectively. A laminated FeCrAlY + 25v/o mullite sample also showed only weight gain, to a maximum of $1.3\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$. Weight change measurements in oxidation experiments can be ambiguous, if weight losses due to spallation are balanced by gains due to the addition of oxygen. However, for the samples tested, no dimensional change was noted, and the oxide scale present was minimal. Hence, the structures are extremely resistant to air oxidation.

Figure 2

Thermal expansion behavior of low pressure plasma deposits of FeCrAlY with 0 and 25v/o alumina, compared to α -alumina.

Figure 3

Microstructure of FeCrAlY - 25v/o alumina composite after 1000 one oxidation cycles to 1150°C .

Scale adhesion appears to be somewhat better for the composites than for FeCrAlY alone, as noted by the positive weight changes for three of the four composite samples, compared to weight loss for both monolithic FeCrAlY samples. From the thermal expansion data shown in Figure 2, there should be less tendency for spallation of the protective scale in the composite case because of the decreased expansion mismatch between the scale and the substrate. It is unclear what is happening at the interface between Al_2O_3 laminates in the composite and the Al_2O_3 growing on the exposed FeCrAlY regions. From the data for the 5v/o Al_2O_3 composite, it appears that a small addition of oxide may have a detrimental effect on spallation. This may be due to a mechanical interaction between the thin scale and the coarse Al_2O_3 in the composite. The effect might not be counterbalanced in the structures with expansion behavior closest to FeCrAlY.

Another point can be made from consideration of the microstructure in Figure 3. After 1000 hours of cyclic high temperature exposure, there is no apparent interaction between the Al_2O_3 and FeCrAlY. No agglomeration is observed, indicating the structure has excellent morphological stability.

Yield strength, as measured at 0.0025cm offset deflection of the ring samples, is shown as a function of temperature in Figure 4. At room temperature, the composites have low ductility, and this is accentuated by the bending stresses generated in the ring test. The 25v/o Al_2O_3 structure showed only elastic deflection at failure, so no room temperature yield strength is shown for that composite. Figure 4 indicates a strengthening by the composite approach, with strengthening increasing with increasing volume fraction of Al_2O_3 . The yield strength of FeCrAlY is increased ~50% at room temperature, and as much as 300% at 1010°C. Ultimate tensile strength showed a similar relation. These data indicate that although Al_2O_3 is present as a laminate rather than filaments, strengthening is achieved. Figure 5 shows that ductility, as measured by plastic deflection of the ring in tension, increases with increasing temperature, but decreases with increasing fraction of Al_2O_3 . For some applications, specific strength may be more important than absolute strength. The density of the 25v/o Al_2O_3 structure, 6.15g/cm^3 , is approximately 11% lower than the 6.88g/cm^3 value for FeCrAlY, so that specific yield strength of the composite represents an even larger gain over the FeCrAlY deposit, to values of 340% at 1010°C.

The continuous laminate (Figure 1a) composites also showed substantial benefits in strength compared to FeCrAlY. These structures were produced by putting FeCrAlY powder in one feeder, and Al_2O_3 in a second feeder, then alternately feeding the powders to the plasma. By controlling feed rate and length of spray time, the volume fraction and interlaminar spacing can

be varied. As before, 0.1cm thick tubes were deposited and ring samples made. For all samples, the inner and outer layers were FeCrAlY. For structures made with 6 passes of FeCrAlY and 2 of alumina or mullite, there were 20 ceramic layers through the 0.1cm thick ring. For the 12 pass/4 pass structures, there were 10 layers of ceramic. The ceramic layers made up approximately 25v/o of the structure, and were each 10 or 20 μ m thick for

Figure 4

Yield strength at 0.0025cm offset as a function of temperature for low pressure plasma deposits of FeCrAlY and FeCrAlY matrix composites.

Figure 5

Deflection after yielding as a function of temperature for low pressure plasma deposits of FeCrAlY and FeCrAlY matrix composites.

the 6/2 and 12/4 structures. The 8/2 and 16/4 structures again had 10 or 20 μ m layers of ceramic, but now the ceramic was only 20v/o of the structure. For these composites, there were either 18 or 9 ceramic layers in the 0.1cm thick rings.

Data for the continuous laminate composites are shown in Table I. The remarkable feature of the data is the similarity of results, essentially independent of volume fraction, interlaminar spacing, or of whether alumina or mullite was the ceramic. Compared to the mixed (discontinuous laminate) 25v/o alumina structure in Figures 4 and 5, the continuous laminates were weaker at high temperatures, and generally more ductile over the entire temperature range.

Comparison has been made of FeCrAlY ring properties to standard bar properties for conventionally cast FeCrAlY of the same composition. The plasma deposit was equivalent to the casting.

TABLE I
Ring Tensile Data for FeCrAlY Continuous Laminate Composites

Material	T (°C)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Ext. (mm)	Material	T (°C)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Ext. (mm)
6 passes FeCrAlY	RT	636	636	0	12 passes FeCrAlY	RT	No Yield	490	-
2 passes Alumina	560	364	401	0.7	4 passes Alumina	560	376	399	0.7
	710	157	175	1.4		710	147	166	1.3
	860	81	89	1.6		860	63	72	1.1
	1010	47	54	1.0		1010	52	54	0.6
8 passes FeCrAlY	RT	641	650	0.08	16 passes FeCrAlY	RT	680	715	0.05
2 passes Alumina	560	373	401	1.1	4 passes Alumina	560	376	394	1.1
	710	139	175	2.4		710	167	188	0.9
	860	83	90	1.2		860	88	93	0.8
	1010	45	49	0.9		1010	46	47	1.0
6 passes FeCrAlY	RT	643	643	0	12 passes FeCrAlY	RT	663	685	0.05
2 passes Mullite	560	369	419	0.5	2 passes Mullite	560	361	404	1.1
	710	163	188	1.3		710	143	177	1.3
	860	87	89	1.1		860	88	91	1.4
	1010	41	49	1.1		1010	42	50	1.2

T: temperature
YS: yield strength at .0025cm offset
UTS: ultimate tensile strength
Ext: plastic extension of ring
RT: room temperature

ring samples
3.8cm ID
0.33cm wide
0.10cm thick
test cross-sectional
area = 0.066cm²

cross-head motion: 0.05cm/min
all tests in air

SUMMARY

Composite structures consisting of a FeCrAlY matrix and either alumina or mullite laminates can be prepared by low pressure plasma deposition. The structures are sound metallurgically, with almost complete absence of porosity.

In expansion, the materials follow approximately a rule-of-mixtures behavior. Cyclic oxidation at 1150C indicates excellent resistance to the air environment, with the composites having somewhat less spallation of the protective scale than does FeCrAlY itself. The 1000 hour cyclic exposures showed the structures to be morphologically very stable.

Mechanical behavior of the composites was also substantially better than FeCrAlY. Tensile tests showed gains of up to 1.5X at room temperature, and 3.4X at 1010°C, in specific yield strength. Discontinuous laminates were the strongest in tensile tests, and monolithic FeCrAlY was the most ductile.

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